

The Dark Sides of Modern Science: Ethics, Morality, Values and Professionalism

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Abstract: This is the fourth article in our series “The Dark Sides of Modern Science” and is about ethics, morality, values and professionalism in science (and knowledge in general). The remarks that we stated in the Introduction of the first article of this series (i.e. “Knowledge Production and Authoring”) generally apply to this article and hence we do not need to repeat.

Keywords: Ethics of science, ethics of knowledge, morality in science, academic misconduct, corruption in science, corruption related to science.

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1 Fraud, Fabrication, Cheating and Dishonesty

Also see sections like “Paper Mills” and “Manipulation of Knowledge” in the previous publications of this series.

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3 Gender Disparity, Misogyny and Sexism

Also see sections like "Bias and Disparity in Academic Publishing" in the previous publications of this series.

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4 Ethnic Disparity and Racism

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5 Other Disparities in Academia

For gender disparity see § 3, and for ethnic disparity see § 4. Also see sections like “Bias and Disparity in Academic Publishing” in the previous publications of this series.

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7 Academic Freedom and Freedom in Academia

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8 Conflict of Interest

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47. [Conflict of Interest Principles and Examples.](#)
48. [Conflicts of interest in academic publishing.](#)
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50. [Conflict of interest in research: what is it and why it matters?.](#)

51. [Perspectives on ‘Conflicts of interest’.](#)
52. [Examples of Conflicts of Interest.](#)
53. [How Conflicts of Interest Shape Trust in Academic Work.](#)
54. [Non-financial conflicts of interest.](#)
55. [Post-publication conflicts of interest.](#)
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9 Exploitation and Free-Riding

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16. Exploitation by supervisors must stop.
17. It's time to stand up to greedy academic publishers.
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19. Young person in Academia: I'm tired of being exploited and humiliate. Is it just me?.
20. Opinion: Exploitation persists in academic science-here's what we can do.
21. 'Hope labour': is Academia exploitative?.
22. Care Exploitation in Academia.
23. The exploitation trap of hope labour.
24. Enough of exploiting academics - now pay us fairly.
25. Staff Exploitation and Redundancies in UK Universities.
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27. Ethics dumping: the exploitative side of academic research.
28. US Colleges and Universities Are Becoming Giant Exploitation Machines.
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30. Labour rights are not the solution to PhD exploitation.
31. Personal Experiences of Exploitation of Research Students by Professors.
32. PhD Student Exploitation.
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34. Silence means consent: a manifesto against exploitation in academia.
35. Ghost Authoring: How Professors Steal the Work of Their Students.
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19. [Did you know, that abuse of power in academia takes many different forms?.](#)
20. [Power abuse and anonymous accusations in academia - Perspectives from early career researchers and recommendations for improvement.](#)
21. [University Members Discuss Abuse of Power.](#)
22. [The Silent Scandal - Power Abuse and Corruption by Design in German Research.](#)

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24. [Academic power abuse is a structural issue - not just individual misconduct.](#)
25. [Study on abuse of power: University responds with 7-point plan.](#)

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Also see sections like “Fraud, Fabrication, Cheating and Dishonesty” (refer to § 1) as well as sections like “Contract Cheating and Essay Mills” in the previous papers of this series.

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15. Understanding Fake Degrees and Credential Fraud in Higher Ed.
16. Fake degrees: the secret industry damaging so many employers.
17. 'Staggering' trade in fake degrees revealed.
18. Why Are So Many People Buying Fake PhDs?.
19. Everything you need to know about fake degrees and the 'universities' awarding them.
20. UK degree fraud: 85 fake university websites taken down in five years.
21. Non-recognised HEIs and Diploma Mills.
22. Diploma Mills and Accreditation.
23. Understanding Diploma Mills and Recognising Legitimate Online Learning.
24. Degree Mills: An Old Problem & A New Threat.
25. Checking for admissions fraud.
26. Varsity Blues scandal.
27. The perfectly legal - but immoral - ways rich kids get into top colleges.
28. Celebrity parents and the bizarre 'cheating' scandal.
29. College Admissions Scandal.
30. Safeguarding higher education admissions: Identifying red flags in student application documentation.
31. US college admissions scandal: how did the scheme work and who was charged?.
32. College admission scandal grew out of a system that was ripe for corruption.
33. Operation Varsity: How the rich and famous cheated the US university system.
34. Operation Varsity Blues: The College Admissions Scandal.
35. 5 things to know about the college admissions scandal.
36. By the Numbers: Academic Integrity in Higher Education.
37. Welcome to college, you can probably get away with cheating.
38. Is the College Cheating Scandal the 'Final Straw' for Standardized Tests?.
39. SAT Cheating Scandal.
40. The college admissions scandal shed light on an academic epidemic.
41. Mark Riddell: Exam whizz at centre of US college cheat scandal.
42. SAT Scores of Asian Students Cancelled Over Cheating.
43. Here's how the students were able to cheat on SAT exams in college admissions scandal.
44. Chinese nationals accused of taking SATs for others.
45. Why It's So Easy to Cheat on College Admissions Tests Like the SAT.
46. Cheating claims delay SAT test scores in China, South Korea.

47. [The Perfect Score: Cheating on the SAT.](#)
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50. [75 fake universities closed in UK.](#)
51. [Another Exciting AI Application: Creating Fake Universities.](#)
52. [NUC Blacklists 58 Fake Universities Operating in Nigeria.](#)
53. [Inside a Network of Fake College Websites.](#)
54. ["Fake" colleges.](#)
55. [There is a bigger problem than bogus or fake universities.](#)
56. [NUC Publishes List of 58 Fake Universities, Warns Against Illegal Degrees.](#)
57. [More than 30 fake universities shutdown as government commissions international clampdown.](#)
58. [Focus On: Degree Fraud.](#)
59. [Diploma certificate templates.](#)
60. [Spotting a Fake Education Certificate.](#)
61. [Online Certificate Maker.](#)
62. [7 ways to spot a fake degree certificate.](#)
63. [Fake diploma scandal rattles faith in Turkish state.](#)
64. [Here's How to Spot a Fake Diploma.](#)
65. [High School Diploma Scams.](#)
66. [How to Make a Diploma Certificate in 4 Minutes!.](#)
67. [Buy Authentic UK College and University Diplomas & Transcripts.](#)
68. [Diploma Maker.](#)
69. [Same Day Novelty Certificates.](#)

12 CV Padding and Resume Fraud

In fact, there is extensive literature about “CV Padding and Resume Fraud” and related issues in general,^[1] but the literature related to academia and research specifically is limited. The following may be examples of “CV Padding and Resume Fraud” in academia and research (or related to this category):

^[1]The following is an example of this literature:

M. Cleary; G. Walter; D. Jackson. Editorial: ‘Is that for real?’: curriculum vitae padding, 2013. DOI: [10.1111/jocn.12161](https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.12161).

1. C.M. Snyder; O.M. Zidar. Resume Padding Among Economists, 2011.
DOI: [10.2139/ssrn.1986219](https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1986219)
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4. [Ensuring you are hiring qualified research staff: Guarding against CV padding.](#)
5. [How to Pad Your CV.](#)
6. [Study: 'Resume padding' prevalent in college-bound students who volunteer.](#)

13 Nepotism, Cronyism and Patronage

Also see sections like “Conflict of Interest” (refer to § 8) as well as sections like “Bias and Disparity in Academic Publishing” in the previous papers of this series.

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8. J. Ruth; M. Berube. From Professionalism to Patronage, 2015.
DOI: [10.1057/9781137506122_4](https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137506122_4)
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11. N. Nosengo. Italy's anti-nepotism drive picked up in surname study, 2017. DOI:

- [10.1038/nature.2017.22242](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2017.22242)
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14 Spamming, Phishing and Intrusion

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